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Editor's note

The Copernican revolution represented the scientific and conceptual change that eliminated the Earth as the centre of the universe. Such was the impact of this new way of thinking that the term Copernican turn has become equivalent to a radical change in any discipline. Today, a second Copernican revolution, as it has been called, is a challenge that leads us to perceive our planet as a complex and dynamic entity. This complex reality forces the need for intersectoral collaboration: only if there is an interest and a multi-stakeholder commitment will it be possible to face the socio-ecological challenges we face. The articulating links for collaboration need the commitment of transformative agents not only from academia but also from industry, government, and the inclusion of other holders of equally expert knowledge, but not recognised as such. In collaborative aspects, we are all interested parties, actors, agents or stakeholders, both locally and globally.

In this issue, you will find an article by Paola Massyel García Meneses on the historical collaborations between academia, government and industry, and how they have influenced each other, to now aspire to a university oriented towards transdisciplinary. The second article, by Salvador Garcilita, delves into the characteristics, impact and challenges of intersectoral productions with a network approach and the complexity that arises from cooperation links between the actors that participate in a project. In the *CO₂nversing* section, Patricia Pérez Belmont, General Director of Umbela Transformaciones Sostenibles, shares her vision on the strategies and barriers associated with intersectoral collaboration. Of course, we also include some recommendations for further exploring these topics in the *Yes, Yes It Is* and *Take Away* sections.

The university oriented towards transdisciplinary collaboration

By Paola M. García-Meneses
y Adrián Fernández Reyes

Universities are, undoubtedly, some of the oldest institutions in the West that have served as a space for transformation and continuous collaboration, in which the knowledge generated is exposed and influenced by social trends and requirements of the historical context. This does not mean that in the East, educational issues –and the collaborative processes emanating from them– have receded into the background: the formal Chinese educational system dates back just over 2,000 years to the Han dynasty, whose imperial examinations (Keju) were the official method for recruiting public officials. Its modern heir is the famous and feared Gaokao, a test that lasts nine hours and is the only factor determining the possibility for young people to pursue higher studies. A high score guarantees admission to the best universities and, eventually, to better jobs in industry and government.

One of the most evident successes of universities is that, after a thousand years, some of their characteristics –with their respective consequences– still persist. Roland Scholz, one of the pioneers in the theory and practice of transdisciplinarity, elaborated an account of the critical functions and the roles of universities related to science since the beginning of the eleventh century. The first medieval university, the *Universitá di Bologna*, founded in 1088, was organised into faculties and encouraged academic free thought, interest in the local community and, most importantly, specialisation. Performance-based degrees (equivalent to bachelor's, master's, and PhD's) were awarded; earning them meant a better reputation. Of course, the documents that endorsed the degree had the signature of the Pope and the current ruler, which shows the existing ties and collaborations, from the beginning, between sectors, in this case, university and government. This type of conception of the medieval university lasted without much modification until the advent of the French Revolution, mainly for two reasons: 1) the search for a type of professional and technical education (reflected in the *École Polytechnique*, for example) focused on mechanical, chemical and electrical processes linked to industrial and economic activities; and 2) a university education that is strongly defined by the elites in power. At the end of the 18th century, Kant, in his works "The Conflict of the Faculties" and "What is the Enlightenment?" defended the position of philosophy, reason and freedom of expression against the existence of a university oriented (and even defined) by the elites. One of the most relevant points was that the leading "careers" (theology, law, and medicine) often served government interests. Otherwise, they were unfunded (which also doesn't sound far off or far-fetched nowadays).

The first transformation of academic institutions was the teaching-research relationship. It started in the 17th-18th century and originated due to the German university reform. Wilhelm von Humboldt, a Prussian scholar, skilled civil servant and older brother of the scientist-traveller Alexander, promoted a new university scheme in which teaching and research were inseparable as the core responsibilities of a professor. In the German universities of the 19th century, small groups of students were allowed a direct and daily relationship with their professors, a student-professor relationship. The teachers trained the students by making them participants in the research work. Consequently, new learning spaces, such as laboratories and new forms of analysis and discussion, such as academic seminars, were created. The research activity was transformed into a way of study for both teachers and students, with which a network for advancing knowledge was proposed through the conformation of the research-teaching-academic relationship triad (Wolfson, 1962).

Subsequently, this model was extended to the rest of the world and premises and criteria for linking the production and dissemination of knowledge were established. At the end of the 19th century, the adoption of this model in American and European universities and the financing of public and research institutes resulted in an important scientific development and, with it, a disciplinary boom that made university organisations more intricate. Certain disciplines and the degree of specialisation even gave academic identity to university institutions, considered places and repositories to preserve knowledge. In addition, the division into disciplines prevented, in a certain way, that knowledge was too abstract or that there was too much information to be covered.

Other important changes in university collaborations with other sectors of society occurred with the conflicts and wars of the 20th century. During World War II, for example, a breakthrough in military research led to the creation of interdisciplinary groups focused on both theory and application of science. The war processes led to the need to join efforts between different disciplines to plan war operations strategically. The problem-solving response involved the collaborative creation of game theory, operations research, cybernetics, and cryptography, for example. After the Second World War, although the disciplines obviously survived, many scientists began to work in large programs as knowledge workers for problem-solving and in the transformation and creation of industries through methodologies that involved a cross between knowledge of different disciplines.

Of course, conflicts and wars also fostered the alignment of science with political positions or the expulsion and the scientific diaspora in case of opposing them. Of course, the political regimes that influenced the issues and the type of research carried out during and after the wars were crucial for the history of science and universities. For example, some German academics aligned themselves with Hitler's political positions; however, academics who escaped those regimes founded other groups in France or the United States. An important case was the group of Hungarian mathematicians and physicists who found asylum in the United States and were called Martians due to their genius and marked accent when speaking English (von Neumann, von Kármán, Teller, Pólya, Erdos, among others). Eventually, the involvement of the Martians led to equally controversial projects for the Russians and Soviets, such as the Manhattan Project. In Germany, for example, the nuclear physics, that some Jewish scientists had developed, was replaced by Aryan Physics, obviously nationalist in nature. The dissolution and dissemination of the intellectual luminaries that made up the Vienna Circle (Schlick, Neurath, Carnap, Gödel, Reichenbach) or the Frankfurt school of philosophy (Horkheimer, Adorno, Fromm, Benjamin, Bloch) led to migrations in science that modified the type of links with other sectors of society. Some ideas that remained after the migrations of scientists meant a setback in scientific advances, such as Lysenkoism, promoted by Trofim Lysenko against natural selection and Mendelian genetics. With Lysenko's urging and Stalin's authorisation, several geneticists were executed or sent to concentration camps. The prevailing ideologies even led to the fact that, in 1948, genetics was declared a bourgeois pseudoscience.

In the 1960s, student movements had a great impact on the role of universities and their impact on society. At the same time, a clear separation emerged between the role of public universities for the masses and that of elite universities (generally private and with high admission fees).

These movements were markedly interdisciplinary. Subsequently, the need to manage complex and interconnected issues between disciplines was raised because the connection between knowledge and society is indissoluble. This led to the need to define the research problems and objectives together, to carry out their representation and transformation based on mutual learning. In this way, transdisciplinary research processes were detonated, which, according to Stokols, implies not only the integration of approaches but also the creation of new frameworks, hypotheses and conceptual research strategies that synthesise diverse perspectives, ultimately extending beyond to transcend pre-existing disciplinary boundaries. During the 1980s, and with the inclusion of more innovative careers that from the beginning put transdisciplinarity as a way of addressing problems (mainly environmental), programs such as sustainability sciences emerged, which involve close collaboration between society and academia and diverge from or distance themselves from the concept and practice of knowledge commercialisation that is adopted in many universities around the world (Fernández et al. 2000).

The tradition of the disciplines has been to approach “a part” –with its own language, methods and borders–, in contrast to the study of “the whole” as a phenomenon. For the study of the socio-ecological problems that concern us, disciplinary immersion, however deep it may be, is insufficient.

Consequently, at this crossroads, it is essential to review the social function of the university. Given that the traditional university is currently in crisis, it is necessary to build a new model more in line with today's world. This makes sense since we recognise that the needs and demands placed on universities differ greatly from those of the tradition with which these institutions were conceived. The medieval university, in its etymological sense, the medieval university had the universal as its object. Transdiscipline is closer to this original sense since it implies openness to reflections beyond disciplines and constructing a new paradigm of different unifying levels of reality and perception. For this reason, transdisciplinary emphasises the need for a change of vision in which disciplinarity has been necessary and where the benefit of science and technology is undeniable, but which has also led to excesses that place us, perhaps, in the Ragnarök of the Anthropocene; in our final battle. Fortunately, not all is lost. There can be no transdisciplinary without a previous and deeply transited state of the disciplinary vision. The reality fragmented by the disciplinary vision can be reconstructed from the transdisciplinary since it allows a systemic and overall vision that considers the transversality of knowledge, where knowledge impacts the whole and where there is unity in diversity.

This brief historical analysis offers a panorama where the university has become a heterogeneous and multifaceted institution that reacts to the historical needs of society. The wide range of universities shares the organisational model of the University of Bologna. They deal with cultural and human materials in universalist terms (Ramirez et al. 2016) but are highly diversified regarding objectives, profiles and quality. Universities range from various elite institutions in which most of the historical features of Bologna, Humboldt and the disciplinary university are still visible to a still growing number of regional or applied knowledge institutions oriented towards specific professional teaching. According to Scholz, universities face a crossroads with paths towards different ways of doing science for and with society. This is a process of diversification and a new moment of transformation for academic institutions, which, as we have seen, adapt to emerging situations and regenerate ties in the face of adversity. Transdiscipline-oriented transformations within universities generally bring benefits and new insights into how to co-produce and share knowledge. Still, they also face reluctance and slow adoption within classical institutions, stuck in archaic and outdated methods mainly dedicated to transferring knowledge and not its co-production.

Transdisciplinarity theory is a 20th-century product of philosophical reflection renewed by discoveries in quantum physics, general systems theory, and computer science advances. For this reason, in the vision of Basarab Nicolescu, one of the basic driving elements of transdisciplinary arises from the studies of quantum mechanics: Bell's theorem, which gives birth to the concept of non-separability. In classical physics, the interaction between two receding objects diminishes until it disappears. In contrast, in the quantum world, the interaction remains, regardless of the distance. That is, the interactions make sense because all other possible interactions exist. In collaborative terms, the term synergy is appropriate since it refers to the fact that the parts are inseparable in a system and that the whole in operation emerges from them. This same meaning of synergy must permeate the action and vision of the university, understood as a system and a space where human groups converge and must put a new "everything" into operation, adapted to current socio-ecological problems. In particular, a new perspective is urgently needed to observe the complex nature of reality holistically and systemically. Transdisciplinarity thus constitutes a different perspective to address new stories, narratives and chapters in collaboration with other sectors of society, from openness, responsibility, empathy and, above all, the perennial and simultaneous presence of the objective, the subjective and the sacred.

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1] Interdisciplinary research is a modality that integrates information, data, techniques, tools, perspectives, concepts or theories from two or more disciplines or bodies of specialized knowledge to acquire fundamental knowledge to solve problems where solutions go beyond the scope of a single discipline or research area (Smith, 2016).

TRACING IMPACT THROUGH INTERSECTORAL NETS

BY **Salvador Garcilita Arguello** (GIZ - Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit GmbH, The German Agency for International Cooperation; Instituto Tecnológico Autónomo de México [ITAM]).

Sustainability projects are, at least at some point, oriented towards generating impact. Certainly, although the impact of a project must be something that endures and evolves over time, it is not usually static. The impact approach, in the context of public programs and policies, allows us to model the interventions' scope across different spatiotemporal scales in a given system; no small challenge when complexity arises from so many levels and scales whose interaction must be taken into account (even small organisations, as a result of their internal rules, processes and identity, generate their own emergent properties, independent of the flow of personnel that make them up).

To represent the complexity of collaboration, we did an exercise and graphed a real-world project cooperation system which is defined in the following graph or net (see Fig 1) that represents a real-world cooperation system as $G = (n,v)$, where the nodes (colour dots) n represent actors involved in the implementation of an international cooperation project, and v (black lines) the interaction between those actors and the main components of a specific program. Nodes are classified by colour.

Proportionally, large nodes represent institutions; small nodes represent individual actors whose participation was significant enough to be mapped apart from their corresponding institution, or simply their engagement was independent of their affiliated organisation.

Figure 1. Blue nodes are the main components of the project; red nodes represent primary actors, those who are directly affected by the project; yellow nodes represent secondary actors who participate in the project indirectly or temporarily; green nodes are associated with key actors, those who can significantly influence the project for their capacities, knowledge, or position. Finally, pink nodes represent influential actors with veto power; their participation or support is indispensable for the project's success.

This model represents actual data. There are two patterns to highlight (without the name labels for each node and context of the project, they would go unnoticed). First, right in the graph's centre are two "institutional" nodes, one represented by green and the other by blue dots. The blue represents the project's core, the programme as an entity. The green one, with which the blue one mentioned above overlaps, is the main counterpart of this international cooperation project: a local government institution with common objectives and shared responsibilities in the project's area of influence. Note how it is linked to the same main components and therefore deals with the same actors. This close alignment is intentional and results from the co-creation and co-implementation strategy of the project.

The second aspect to highlight is simple and can be easily overlooked as it seems obvious but notice how some actors are linked to more than one project component. This may occur more often than expected, either directly or indirectly, and requires special consideration. Denying or ignoring these relationships in a cooperative system does not diminish their influence and could lead to neglecting potential synergies or conflicts.

Indeed, this network is a minimalist approach developed at such a level of abstraction that it helps to understand the connectivity between actors in this cooperation project but leaves aside other interactions that might exist (for example, between the mapped institutions). However, due to the high number of vertices connecting the nodes, such a complex network would only be readable and understandable with special tools such as the index and other metrics.

The purpose of this graph is not to evidence collaboration between individual institutions (which is why the associated names of each point or node were removed) but to highlight the complexity of a cooperative system. Complex real-world systems have many more interactions, some dynamic and emergent, which are often beyond our knowledge and understanding and can significantly impact the dynamics of cooperation (and thus on the programme itself).

An intrinsic problem of the impact approach is how it is conceptualised and measured in different institutions and organisations. Indeed, proposing and standardising metrics for impact measurement is a current challenge in sustainability sciences. As in any field of research, the data's veracity must be considered. Figure 2 shows an approach to how the impact was measured in other English-language sustainability projects/research, which resulted from a systematised literature review (specifically, a configurative systematic search) of the Google Academics repository using keywords related to impact in the context of sustainability projects for the years 2000-2020. As a result, 81 documents of different types (research articles, theses, and corporate reports) were analysed. From this search, the question arises whether there is a bias on how impact measurement is being conceptualised and which sectors are developing it the most.

Figure 2. The number of counts per topic related to academic, environmental, economic and social impact.

In addition, with a simple data mining search, we could visualise a "cloud" of the first three keywords of each document, where the size and colour of each word are congruent and proportional to the number of occurrences. Do you see a trend?

Figure 3. Word cloud generated from data mining.

As mentioned above, impact in the context of sustainability projects is an open field of research. These graphs preview the results of an ongoing collaboration at the National Laboratory of Sustainability Sciences (UNAM); hopefully, supra-organizational and cross-sectoral collaboration can lead to a deeper and enriched understanding of how impact might be conceptualised in a global context.

Nature has many mutualistic examples (benefit for all participants) where cooperation is essential to achieve more meaningful goals. In the end, the success of an intervention derived from a project is determined by the appropriate technical and political procedure, the methodological approach, and the coupling of its participants. For this, communication and negotiation are critical and require the collaborative development of learning and innovations through the exchange of experiences and knowledge, leading to the co-creation of imperative hows after declarative whats; this could be a sine qua non-condition for successful cooperation.

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CONVERSING

Barriers to intersectoral collaboration

Interview with **Patricia Pérez Belmont**, by **Paola Massyel García Meneses**

A biologist by training, she has a Master's degree in Biological Sciences. She is currently a doctoral candidate in the Postgraduate Program in Sustainability Sciences at the National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM). Her research focuses on understanding agricultural change processes in urban contexts based on the study of decision-making processes that result in the prevalence or abandonment of agriculture and affect urban resilience and sustainability. Patricia has experience designing and coordinating projects from civil society and with the private sector on issues of citizen science, environmental monitoring of aquatic socio-ecosystems, and implementation of sustainable productive activities for conservation. She has also collaborated as a consultant in governmental projects and with academia thanks to her experience using inter- and transdisciplinary participatory tools and methodologies for research and the design of public policies in socio-ecological systems. As part of her career and professional training, she has dedicated herself to teaching at the high school and college levels at the UNAM Faculty of Sciences. Patricia has scientific and outreach publications, has participated in national and international conferences and is an associate editor for a special Journal of Freshwater Science issue. Due to her work and experience with civil society on conservation issues, she was invited by the Department of State of the United States of America through the Bureau of Educational and Cultural Affairs of the US Embassy in Mexico to participate in the "International Visitor Leadership Program, Environmental Engagement and the Economy".

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Patricia-Perez-Belmont>
<https://www.linkedin.com/in/patricia-p%C3%A9rez-belmont-a261397a/>

Cross-sector collaboration is essential for sustainability because no single sector or organisation can solve the complex challenges humanity faces nowadays. Sustainability issues are complex and interconnected, requiring diverse perspectives, knowledge, and resources to address them effectively. For example, we need cooperation in public, private, and civil society to address climate change. The public sector can provide regulatory frameworks and policies that encourage sustainable practices, while the private sector can bring innovations, technologies and investments to apply them. Civil society, including non-governmental organisations, can promote critical processes of capacity building, education, and social pressure to encourage sustainable behaviours and hold other actors accountable for their environmental impacts.

Similarly, collaboration between different sectors is essential to address social sustainability issues, such as poverty, inequality and access to basic needs. The public sector can provide social safety networks and policies that address systemic inequalities. In contrast, the private sector can create employment opportunities, support fair wages and supply chains, and invest in local communities. Civil society can contribute to grassroots initiatives, community organisation and the defence of human rights. To summarise, collaboration across sectors is vital for sustainability because it enables a collective effort to achieve shared goals, promotes integrated and holistic approaches, and maximises the impact of resources and expertise. Only through collaboration can we achieve more sustainable trajectories that balance socio-ecosystems. Regarding collaboration with other sectors, we had the opportunity to talk with the candidate for PhD, Patricia Pérez Belmont, Director of Umbela Transformaciones Sostenibles, A.C.

For you, why is it relevant to collaborate in an intersectoral way?

For me, cross-sector collaboration is essential, as it involves bringing together people with different backgrounds, approaches, experiences, knowledge and perspectives. This diversity enriches the discussions on various issues and problems and, therefore, also the ability to generate creative solutions to address underlying problems and not superficially. Bringing together people from different sectors to address specific issues also means a union of efforts and resources that are necessary to address complex problems; These resources can be financial, but also experiences and support networks can be used to achieve the objectives of the collaboration. I also believe that a correctly planned intersectoral partnership can make the work much more efficient since, in terms of the distribution of tasks, these can be oriented according to the sector. The greatest virtue for me would be that through intersectoral collaborations, a much more significant impact can be generated since the proposed objectives and goals can cover various sectors: social, economic, and environmental, among others. The above depends on what we understand by sector. I think that the term sometimes makes us think of formal groups with particular experience or even involvement in a certain area or activity, but, for me, the sectors are different interest groups that may or may not be representative of formal figures (for example, the academia or government), but rather groups that include diverse communities of practice, community groups, indigenous groups, etc.

What do you consider to be the most complicated aspects (barriers) of collaborating with other sectors?

I believe that, although intersectoral collaboration seeks to achieve common objectives, it is difficult for each sector to abandon its work agendas and, therefore, its purposes and priorities, which could also be opposed or conflict with the objectives of other sectors. Even having common objectives, there may be difficulties in terms of the legal and regulatory frameworks that apply to each sector, which may pose obstacles when proposing collaboration routes, meeting goals, and using specific metrics or indicators, among others. Another critical barrier for me would be language or terminology since how something is conceived or conceptualised can hinder communication between sectors, mainly if people from different cultures are included in the collaborative work since they may have different styles of work, writing and communication that can make intersectoral work difficult.

Intersectoral collaboration also implies a change in attitudes, learning and adaptation processes that take time and suggest a departure from the status quo. This can generate some resistance to change or resistance to the process, both due to the willingness of the participants and the need to invest time, resources and coordination efforts. Another barrier is power dynamics: one sector has more influence than others, preventing a good balance in participation and decision-making. In addition, power dynamics can also alter trust towards one sector or another.

What have been your strategies to overcome these barriers, and what would you recommend?

I recommend taking extreme care in planning, executing, and monitoring an intersectoral collaborative process. Taking care of the process should focus on raising awareness and building trust among participants from different sectors to enhance empathy and flexibility, which are key factors in collaboration. Communication is also crucial in intersectoral collaboration processes; This will depend on whether there is a common understanding of the objectives and priorities, that a common language is jointly developed, and that the constraints (for example, resources or legal obstacles) are explicit.

Given that an intersectoral project or work supposes that the participants of each sector invest considerable time and effort, I would suggest considering the participation of one more actor who acts as a facilitator of the intersectoral collaborative process and who is precisely in charge of monitoring the care of the process, for example, through promoting schemes that guarantee an equitable representation of the sectors, seeking strategies that address power dynamics, ensuring the transparency of the processes and monitoring communication so that it is constant and precise enough.

Thinking about the environmental/sustainability sector, what do you think of the collaboration of visions that historically have been considered conflicting?

Due to conflicting visions, I can think of the approach or term of sustainable development, which is an approach that seeks to integrate both the economic and the environmental and that has been a way of continuous development based on the exploitation of resources and generation of capital, but incorporating the idea of meeting the needs of current and future generations, ensuring the maintenance and care of natural systems. But precisely, this turns out to be a fallacy for many since it leaves aside the historical debt of social and environmental injustices that development and capitalism itself have left in the world —specifically in the countries of the Global South. However, I believe that this problem has also led to the recognition of the need not to reconcile visions but to recognise that there are different visions and that they can all be accommodated; the need to dialogue, to work with systemic and holistic approaches, to take advantage of innovation opportunities and to seek shared values such as socio-environmental justice, equity, respect and plurality.

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

Collaboration challenges

From academia, industry or government, people who carry out collaborative work must participate as a team, and in a balanced way, in the design of research agendas, action plans and strategies for implementing an idea. Of course, one of the biggest challenges in this regard is to truly carry out a collaborative effort. In this section we compile some data that could be relevant to trigger reflections on the importance of collaboration and the challenges associated with it.

Seven rules for cultivating collaboration¹

Develop habits of reflexivity: explore your own discipline through the perspective or gaze of other disciplines.

Co-create the project management plan from an early stage: include milestones and deadlines to achieve some objective.

Speak the same language: adopt a language appropriate to an inclusive environment. If you do not understand, ask. If you understand, answer. Respect diversity, different academic backgrounds and other knowledge, and experiences.

Design for the collective benefit: the planning of a project must incorporate the research agenda of all the actors and collaborators.

Illustrate weaknesses in collaborative design from an early stage: correct in a timely manner to give a positive result, and avoid waiting for a product to be "perfect".

Sharing collaboration tools: collaborative documents, shared calendars, instant messaging, repositories, project files, tutorials, etc.

Document collaboration: Evolutionary experiences, reflections, and best practices benefit the entire community. They are historical, community and anecdotal evidence to know what has been done and what works or is useful.

Hybrid conception of transdisciplinary collaborations²

¹ Adapted from Sahneh F, Balk MA, Kisley M, Chan C-k, Fox M, Nord B, et al. (2021) Ten simple rules to cultivate transdisciplinary collaboration in data science. PLoS Comput Biol 17(5): e1008879.

² Adapted from Hoffmann, S., Thompson Klein J., Pohl, C. (2019), Linking transdisciplinary research projects with science and practice at large: Introducing insights from knowledge utilization, Environmental Science & Policy, Volume 102, Pages 36-42, ISSN 1462-9011.

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

Team Collaboration Statistics in 2023

60% of executives expect to invest more in virtual collaboration

Collaborative work consumes 85% of working days

85% of employees have a problem or conflict with virtual meetings

9 out of 10 workers who work with data or in some information sector believe that digital collaboration will continue

49% of employees believe that collaboration is easier in the office

By 2024, virtual meetings will constitute 75% of the conversations of a work team

PARA LLEVAR TAKE-AWAY

Book: *To build the common among the different. Guide for intersectoral collaboration towards sustainability*

A book derived from the workshops for exchanging experiences of Transdisciplinary Collaboration towards Sustainability (2015) that collects knowledge about the different logics of community actors, organised civil society, academia, government and companies. It also addresses the elements that hinder collaboration and some clues that could be useful for those who engage in collaborative initiatives with other sectors.

https://www.uv.mx/personal/galatorre/files/2017/05/P ara_construir_lo_comun_entre_los_diferentes_Gui%CC%81a-para_la_colaboracio%CC%81n_intersectorial_hacia_la_sustentabilidad_VD.pdf

Documentary: *The Brief Spring of Wind Power in Germany*

This DW documentary exposes how the wind energy development strategy in Germany, as part of its energy transition, faces significant technical, social and environmental challenges, which requires collaboration between research groups, industry and government to reduce the risks and conflicts associated with such projects.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UScKhndGfs4>

Book: *Planning for development in Latin America and the Caribbean: approaches, experiences and perspectives*

This book, published by ECLAC (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean) in 2017, presents the challenges of managing the interrelationships under which different sectors, institutions, levels of government and different time frames operate simultaneously through the analysis of case studies of nine countries in the region. This text highlights the importance of addressing the challenges of intersectorality, multi-temporality, multi-scalarity and participation.

<https://www.cepal.org/es/publicaciones/42139-planificacion-desarrollo-america-latina-caribe-enfoques-experiencias>

Documentary: *This is how Norway fights climate change*

This documentary presents two visions to reduce CO₂ emissions in Norway and the Netherlands through CCS and peat recovery, respectively. Two valuable and complementary proposals where industry and academia play a fundamental role.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YhHCRDvOR94>

Mexico City, Mexico 2023